

Clinical Evaluation of Various Materials to Seal the Orifice of Teeth Following Endodontic Treatment

Ruchi Gupta¹, Asit Vats², Priyansh Saxena³, A Pritish Kumar Reddy⁴, Martina George⁵, Shalaka Tayade⁶, Dipasha Sharma⁷, Th Sujata Devi⁸

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Professor¹,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry & Endodontics,
DJ College of Dental Science &
Research,
Modinagar, Ghaziabad

Professor & Head²,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry & Endodontics,
DJ College of Dental Science &
Research,
Modinagar, Ghaziabad

PG students³⁻⁸,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry & Endodontics,
DJ College of Dental Science &
Research,
Modinagar, Ghaziabad

Corresponding Author
Dr. Priyansh Saxena,
PG student,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry & Endodontics,
DJ College of Dental Science &
Research,
Modinagar, Ghaziabad

Abstract

Background: Microbial colonization within the pulp cavity represents a significant contributor to endodontic treatment shortcomings. Therefore, alongside the establishment of a three-dimensional apical seal, the provision of a coronal barrier for root canal obturations has been advocated.

Aim: The current investigation was undertaken to assess and juxtapose the intra-orifice sealing efficacy of two experimental substances subsequent to the completion of root canal system obturation.

Materials and Method: Twenty individuals were selected and root canal treatment was done on mandibular teeth. Gutta-percha was removed to a depth of 3.5 mm from the orifice using a heated plugger. Subsequently, ten specimens were sealed with MTA Angelus and ten with Cention N. Clinical evaluation was done.

Results: Among the materials tested, MTA Angelus exhibited the highest efficacy in achieving clinical success, followed by Cention N.

Conclusion: The present study concluded that the placement of an intraorifice barrier significantly improves the coronal seal and enhances the longevity of post-obturation restorations.

Keywords: Cention N, MTA Angelus, Coronal sealing, intraorifice barrier.

Introduction

The efficacy of endodontic interventions is contingent upon a multitude of factors, encompassing the initial state of the root canal, the presence of periapical lesions, previous endodontic procedures, the quality of root canal filling, and the integrity of coronal restorations. Within this array, microbial infection emerges as a pivotal determinant of treatment failure. Consequently, stringent measures are imperative to forestall microbial ingress into the pulp cavity. A recommended strategy entails ensuring a meticulous coronal seal subsequent to root canal obturation, as the absence thereof can precipitate contamination of the obturated canal, thereby jeopardizing treatment outcomes.¹

A resilient intracanal barrier assumes paramount importance in furnishing an efficacious coronal seal and thwarting the infiltration of bacterial toxins into the root canal—a prerequisite for the success of root canal therapy (RCT).² Suboptimal coronal sealing engenders skepticism regarding the enduring efficacy of treatment, as it exposes obturated canals to microbial colonization, which can impede reparative processes and incite infections in adjacent structures such as the peri-radicular region, periodontal ligament and supporting alveolar bone.

To mitigate these concerns, the

application of a suitable material atop the coronal gutta-percha to serve as a bulwark against coronal microleakage confers substantial benefits in curtailing leakage and augmenting the likelihood of treatment success. The present investigation endeavours to evaluate and juxtapose the effectiveness of these experimental materials in intra-orifice sealing subsequent to root canal obturation.

Material & Methods

Twenty human subjects aged between 20 and 30 years were purposively selected for participation in this study. Endodontic therapy was performed on the molars. Access openings were sealed using cotton pellets and provisional cement to ensure containment and maintain a controlled environment.

Twenty participants were randomly allocated into two groups as follows:

Group 1: MTA Angelus

Group 2: Cention N

Three millimeters of gutta-percha were excised from the coronal orifice (cementodentinal junction) employing Gates Glidden Drills across all teeth. The two

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experimental materials were prepared following the manufacturer's instructions and subsequently applied into the access cavities of their respective groups to effectively seal the orifice. Clinical examination was done.

Discussion

The primary objective of endodontic therapy is the thorough elimination of necrotic debris, microbial pathogens, and their metabolic byproducts, followed by the meticulous obturation of the root canal system. This procedure aims to achieve a hermetic seal, thereby preventing microleakage and thwarting the infiltration of oral fluids and microorganisms into the root canal space.

A myriad of anatomical factors and clinical variables exert influence on the outcome of nonsurgical root canal treatment (RCT). Nevertheless, microleakage emerges as the predominant challenge, significantly impacting the long-term success of endodontic interventions.

Traditionally, inadequate apical seal was attributed as the primary cause of RCT failure, as emphasized by Dow and Ingle. However, contemporary research highlights the critical role of a robust coronal seal in treatment success.

Studies demonstrate that teeth filled with gutta-percha and sealer, lacking temporary restoration, exhibit substantial leakage-ranging from 70 to 85% of the root length-within a mere 56 days of exposure to saliva.³

Literature underscores the urgency of prompt final restoration following RCT. The Iowa group advocates for an immediate and appropriate coronal restoration post-treatment. Glass ionomer cement (GIC) is frequently utilized as an intraorifice barrier. The Himel group at the University of Tennessee observed that teeth devoid of an intraorifice barrier experienced significantly greater leakage compared to those with a glass ionomer intraorifice barrier.

Mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) is a dental biomaterial renowned for its exceptional biocompatibility with oral and dental tissues. MTA Angelus® represents the established original bio ceramic formulation developed by Angelus, noted for its proven efficacy and reliability in clinical applications. MTA Angelus serves as an effective sealing material in

endodontic procedures due to its biocompatibility and bioactive properties, ensuring a durable and biologically favourable seal within the root canal system.

A study by Khanna et al. in 2021 stated that among all the materials, ProRoot MTA shows the best intraorifice sealing ability.⁴

Cention N is a restorative material composed of urethane dimethacrylate, designed to polymerize independently with a powder/liquid formulation, optionally supplemented by light curing. The liquid component consists of dimethacrylate monomers and initiators, while the powder component incorporates various glass fillers, initiators, and pigments. Notably radiopaque, it incorporates alkaline glass fillers capable of releasing fluoride, calcium, and hydroxide ions. The exclusive use of cross-linking methacrylate monomers, coupled with a stable and efficient self-curing initiator system, contributes to Cention N's high polymer network density and achieves a substantial degree of polymerization throughout the entire depth of the restoration. A study by Bhol et al in 2022 stated that Cention N showed the highest sealing ability as compared to packable bulk fill composite and Zirconomer.⁵

Conclusion

The current investigation determined that the inclusion of MTA Angelus as an intraorifice barrier notably enhances the coronal seal and extends the longevity of post-obturation restorations.

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